

Peculiarities of Comprehending the Subjective Well-Being by Student with High and Low Level of Emotional Intelligence

Veronika Pivkina, Alla Kim, Khon Nataliya

Abstract—In this paper, the actuality of the study, and the role of subjective well-being problem in modern psychology and the comprehending of subjective well-being by current students is defined. The purpose of this research is to educe peculiarities of comprehending of subjective well-being by students with various levels of emotional intelligence. Methods of research are adapted Russian-Language questionnaire of K. Riff 'The scales of psychological well-being'; emotional intelligence questionnaire of D. V. Lusin. The research involved 72 students from different universities and disciplines aged between 18 and 24. Analyzing the results of the studies, it can be concluded that the understanding of happiness in different groups of students with high and low levels of overall emotional intelligence is different, as well as differentiated by gender. Students with a higher level of happiness possess more capacity and higher need to control their emotions, to cause and maintain the desired emotions and control something undesirable.

Keywords—Subjective well-being, emotional intelligence, psychology of comprehending, students.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE problem of subjective well-being began to develop since the last decade of 20th century, and it is one of the most important subjects of discussion today [1]. As far as the previous scientific research is concerned, positive emotions help to make the human perception of environment wider, allow to explore and to find new ways of problem's solution [2]. In his speech, the founder of positive psychology as an academic study, Martin Seligman said during the previous 50 years psychology as a science was involved in research and treatment of various pathologies and there wasn't any research about positive aspects of human lives such as creativity, hope or perseverance in achievement of personal purposes and scientist called his colleagues restore a balance [3].

Another actual field of research for psychologists is a problem of emotional intelligence. The pioneers of this problem, J. Mayer and P. Salovey, define emotional intelligence as the ability to realize a meaning of emotions to use these knowledge for understanding of problem's causes and to solve these issues [4].

Veronika Pivkina is with Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Kazakhstan, Bachelor's Degree in Psychology (e-mail: veronikapivkina@yahoo.com).

Alla Kim is an Associate Professor at Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Kazakhstan and holds a PhD Degree in Psychology.

Khon Nataliya is an Associate Professor Russian-Armenian University, Armenia and holds a PhD Degree in Psychology.

Well-known Russian scientist D. V. Lusin related emotional intelligence to problem of comprehending and denoted it as an ability to understand and to estimate own emotions and emotions of other people and as an ability to control own emotions in problem solving [5].

According to the results of modern research, 20% of human success depends on the coefficient of intelligence and 80% of it depends on the coefficient of emotional intelligence [6].

Actuality and novelty of present study are defined, first of all, the role of subjective well-being problem in modern psychology and the comprehending of subjective well-being by current students.

The contemporary world dictates direct requirements to student's competencies. The significant streams of information and frequent communications with people scatter attention of pupils. A solution to this problem is the development of selectivity of attention. The importance in the comprehending process of the core of the subject is the effective side of the mind and positive emotions, which advance efficiency of work in motivation plan.

Today the education should prepare not only professional skills but healthy adaptive successful in all field of life persons who positively estimate nowadays and future. The purpose of research is to educe peculiarities of comprehending of subjective well-being by students with various levels of emotional intelligence.

II. METHODS OF RESEARCH

1. Adapted Russian-language questionnaire of K. Riff «The scales of psychological well-being», which measures each of general level of subjective well-being and its individual components [7].
2. Emotional intelligence questionnaire of D. V. Lusin. This questionnaire diagnoses various components of emotional intelligence, which is determined by the author as the ability to understand own and other people's emotions and as the ability to control them [5], [8].
3. Survey: Our survey is focused on identifying the preferences of the factors of subjective well-being such as Love, Money, Family, Interesting Work, Hobby and so on, taken from the book of M. Argyle "The psychology of well-being". This method we used with the aim of the quality analysis of comprehending of subjective well-being by students on the basis of selected factors for each group of pupils. The research involved 72 students from

different university and disciplines aged between 18 and 24.

III. RESULTS

Subsequent to the results of emotional intelligence questionnaire of D.V. Lusin excerpts of the 72 students aged between 18 and 24 was divided into three groups:

1. Students with a high level of emotional intelligence – 25 people (34,7 %);
2. Students with a middle level of emotional intelligence – 22 people (30,6%);
3. Students with a low level of emotional intelligence – 25 people (34,7 %).

Correlation results of data processing of emotional intelligence questionnaire of D. V. Lusin and the scales of subjective well-being of K. Riff in the program of statistical processing SPSS 20 at a significance level of 0.05 are presented in Table I.

The difference in scale value of subjective well-being, autonomy and self-acceptance between students with high and low levels of emotional intelligence is statistically significant ($p = 0.024$). It is shown that students with a high level of emotional intelligence have higher statistically significant indicators on the scales of autonomy, self-acceptance and subjective well-being than students with low levels of emotional intelligence.

Tables II and III show correlation results of data processing of survey about factors of subjective well-being in the program of statistical processing SPSS 20 at a significance level of 0.05.

TABLE I
CORRELATION RESULTS OF DATA PROCESSING OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE QUESTIONARY OF D.V. LUSIN AND THE SCALES OF SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING OF K. RIFF IN THE PROGRAM OF STATISTICAL PROCESSING SPSS 20 (PIRSON'S COEFFICIENT) [9]

Scales	Interpersonal Intelligence	Intrapersonal Intelligence	Emotional Comprehending	Emotional Control	Emotional Intelligence
Positive Attitude					0,28
Autonomy			0,316		0,312
Media control			0,588	0,306	0,234
Personal Growth	0,681		0,691		0,352
Life's Purposes		0,235			0,285
Self-acceptance	0,522		0,64	0,316	0,468
Subjective Well-Being	0,588	0,663	0,851	0,362	0,724

TABLE II
CORRELATION RESULTS OF DATA PROCESSING OF SURVEY ABOUT FACTORS OF SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING IN THE PROGRAM OF STATISTICAL PROCESSING SPSS 20 AT A SIGNIFICANCE LEVEL OF 0.05 (SPIRMAN'S COEFFICIENT) [9]

Factors	Family	Friendship	Work	Interesting Work	Traveling	Free time, relax
Money			,524**			
Love	,309**					
Family		,603**				,423**
Friendship			,373**	,329**		,358**
Hobby					,498**	
Traveling						,328**

TABLE III
CORRELATION RESULTS OF DATA PROCESSING OF SURVEY ABOUT FACTORS OF SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING IN THE PROGRAM OF STATISTICAL PROCESSING SPSS 20 AT A SIGNIFICANCE LEVEL OF 0.05 (SPIRMAN'S COEFFICIENT) [9]

Factors	Physical Health	Psychological Health	Self-development	Life's purposes	Sense of Humor	Sociability	Altruism	Good sexual relationship
Money								,398**
Love	,396**	,404**						
Family	,625**	,588**	,462**	,463**	,397**	,546**	,403**	
Friendship	,466**	,355**		,373**	,455**	,435**	,317**	,312**
Work				,329**		,342**	,371**	
Interesting Work								,363**
Hobby				,478**	,327**			
Traveling			,309**					
Free time, Relax	,608**	,515**	,332**			,345**	,377**	
Physical Health		,767**	,424**	,384**	,304**	,407**	,390**	
Psychological Health			,402**	,425**	,328**	,473**	,365**	
Self-development				,473**		,366**	,348**	
Life's purposes					,539**	,524**	,399**	
Sense of Humor						,677**	,312**	
Sociability							,570**	
Altruism								,307**

TABLE IV
THE RESULTS OF STATISTICAL ANALYSIS ON THE U-MANN-WHITNEY COEFFICIENT ON THE LEVEL OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE DEPENDING ON THE SCALES OF SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING

	Po	Av	Up	Lr	Cj	Sm	SW
Mann-Whitney U	361,500	428,000	404,500	382,500	297,500	426,000	417,000
Wilcoxon W	685,500	753,000	729,500	707,500	722,500	751,000	742,000
Z	0,952	2,245	1,786	1,360	1,651	2,205	2,028
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0,341	0,025	0,074	0,174	0,099	0,027	0,043
Rank (students with low level of emotional intelligence)	23,54	20,88	21,82	22,70	22,10	20,96	21,32
Rank (students with high level of emotional intelligence)	27,46	30,12	29,18	28,30	28,90	30,04	29,68

TABLE V
THE RESULTS OF STATISTICAL ANALYSIS ON THE U-MANN-WHITNEY COEFFICIENT OF 2 INDEPENDENT SAMPLES BASED ON "SEX" DEPENDING ON THE SCALES OF SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING

	Po	Av	Up	Lr	Cj	Sm	SW
Mann-Whitney U	179,500	244,500	287,500	139,000	231,500	220,000	195,000
Wilcoxon W	479,500	544,500	587,500	439,000	531,500	520,000	495,000
Z	-2,577	-1,313	-0,476	-3,365	-1,565	-1,788	-2,272
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0,010	0,189	0,634	0,001	0,118	0,074	0,023
Rank (women)	30,60	28,10	26,44	32,15	28,60	29,04	30,00
Rank (men)	19,98	22,69	24,48	18,29	22,15	21,67	20,62

TABLE VI
THE RESULTS OF STATISTICAL ANALYSIS ON THE U-MANN-WHITNEY COEFFICIENT OF 2 INDEPENDENT SAMPLES BASED ON "SEX" DEPENDING ON THE SCALES OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

	MI	VI	PE	UE	OI
Mann-Whitney U	223,000	407,000	308,500	344,500	308,000
Wilcoxon W	523,000	707,000	608,500	644,500	608,000
Z	-1,733	1,847	-0,068	0,633	-0,078
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0,083	0,065	0,946	0,527	0,938
Rank (students with low level of emotional intelligence)	28,92	21,85	25,63	24,25	25,65
Rank (students with high level of emotional intelligence)	21,79	29,46	25,35	26,85	25,33

It was determined that the difference in scale value of subjective well-being, personal growth and positive relations between women and men, students aged 18-24 is statistically significant ($p = 0.024$). It is shown women more often than men have higher points of personal growth, positive relations scales and the general level of subjective well-being that confirms many studies on this topic.

The factors of subjective well-being in comprehending of women students with a low level of emotional intelligence aged between 18 and 24 represent blocks: love-family-psychological health.

A group of men - students aged 18-24 years with low levels of emotional intelligence understands subjective well-being widely and the factors that make up the happiness represented 11 proposed factors.

TABLE VII
DISTRIBUTION OF VALUES OF THE SURVEY OF THE FACTORS OF SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING BY STUDENTS FROM DIFFERENT SAMPLES

Group	Students with low level of emotional intelligence		Students with high level of emotional intelligence	
	Sex	Women	Men	Women
Factors			Love	
			Family	
			Friendship	Love
			Work	Family
		Love	Interesting work	Interesting work
		Family	Free time, relax	Physical health
		Psychological health	Physical health	Psychological health
			Psychological health	Self-development
			Self-development	Life's purposes
			Life's purposes	Life's purposes
			Good sexual relationship	Good sexual relationship

A group of women - students aged 18-24 years with a high level of emotional intelligence in the presentation and understanding of subjective well-being includes three main areas:

- Love - family;
- Personal growth - an interesting job;
- Health.

A group of men - students aged 18-24 years with high levels of emotional intelligence includes in their comprehending the following blocks of subjective well-being:

- Love - family;
- Life's purposes - an interesting job;
- Physical health;
- Good sexual relationship.

IV. CONCLUSION

Analyzing the results of this study, one can conclude that the understanding of happiness in different groups of students with high and low levels of overall emotional intelligence is different, as well as differentiated by gender. Also, there is a decrease of factors constituting understanding of happiness in men with high emotional intelligence than men with low emotional intelligence. This may indicate that the concentration and the harmonization of the self-personality and the demonstration of greater autonomy to increase performance on subscales of self-acceptance and autonomy are among the highly emotionally intelligence. Whereas, for women there is an expansion of spheres that make up the happiness, with increasing levels of emotional intelligence, which may also be the result of high levels in the subscales of self-acceptance and autonomy. In all groups, both components

of happiness are a “love-family” block, which indicates the vast importance of this field in the lives of people for positive emotions. Another conclusion is that one of the factors of happiness among both groups of men, unlike women groups, is the quality factor of a sexual relationship. It is also noted that such a factor of happiness as money and income is of no particular value in understanding the happiness of students and is not represented as a factor of happiness of any groups.

One can put forward the assumption that the overall emotional intelligence is being developed in line with the positive emotions and experiences. Because high level of subjective well-being of the student is responsible for the ability to understand the emotional state of a person on the basis of the external manifestations of emotions (facial expressions, gestures, vocal sound), as well as the ability to cause other people have certain emotions, reduce the intensity of unwanted emotions. Such a student can recognize the emotion - establish that there is any emotional feeling in himself or in another person, can identify the emotion, that is, determine what kind of emotion he or another person can feel, finding its verbal expression. He understands the reasons behind the emotion, and the consequences to which it leads. Students with a higher level of happiness possess more capacity and more need to control their emotions, to cause and maintain the desired emotions and control something undesirable. Also, the ability to control the external manifestations of emotions is more expressed, that is, a person can control the intensity of emotions, especially mute strong emotions, can control the outward expression of emotions, may, if necessary randomly cause some emotion. Our study is the first step on this path; we obtained patterns that allow building a clear perspective of practical application in the framework of psychological services at the University.

REFERENCES

- [1] Compton, William C. “1”. An Introduction to Positive Psychology. Wadsworth Publishing, 2005. – 300 p.
- [2] Fredrickson, B. L. The value of positive emotions.// American Scientist, 2003, 91, pp 330-335.
- [3] Martin Seligman. New Positive Psychology: Scientific opinion on the meaning of life and happiness.— M.: «Sophia», 2006. —368 c.
- [4] Mayer J.D., Salovey P. What is Emotional Intelligence? // Emotional Development and Emotional Intelligence; P. Salovey, D.J. Sluyter (Eds.). New York: Basic Books. - 1997. - P. 3-31.
- [5] Lusin D.V. The current thinking about emotional intelligence // Social Intelligence: Theory, measurement, research. - M.: "Institute of Psychology RAS", 2004. - 29–36 pp.
- [6] Goleman D. Emotional Intelligent. - M.: VKT, 2009. – 478 p.
- [7] Shevelenkova T.D., Fesenko P.P. Psychological well-being of the individual (review of basic concepts and methods of the study) // Psychological diagnostics. – 2005. – №3. – C. 95-129.
- [8] Andreeva I.N. Emotional Intelligence: A study of the phenomenon // Questions of psychology. - 2006. - № 3. - C. 78-86.
- [9] Nasledov A.D. SPSS: Computer analysis of the data in psychology and social sciences. - St. Petersburg.: Peter, 2005. - 684 c.